

Study the relationship between Moonlighting and Well being

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ABSTRACT

Moonlighting, defined as engaging in additional employment alongside a primary job, has become increasingly prevalent in contemporary work settings. While it may offer financial and professional benefits, its impact on employees' general well-being remains a subject of concern. The present study aimed to examine the effect of moonlighting on general well-being among working professionals. A sample of 30 participants was selected using purposive sampling, comprising employees engaged in moonlighting and those not involved in additional employment. General well-being was assessed using a WHO-5 well-being Index scale. An independent sample t-test was applied to compare the well-being scores of moonlighters and non-moonlighters. The findings revealed a statistically significant difference between the two groups, indicating that moonlighting has a measurable impact on general well-being. The results highlight the psychological implications of managing multiple job roles and the need for organizational awareness. Further research with larger samples is recommended to enhance generalizability.

Keyword: Moonlighting, General Well-Being, Mental Health, Multiple Employment, t-test.

1. INTRODUCTION

In simple words, moonlighting means doing another job or earning extra income in addition to one's main job. For example, a software engineer working full-time in a company and freelancing as a web developer in the evenings.

Moonlighting has been defined by various authors as the practice of employees engaging in secondary employment in addition to their primary job, often to increase income, develop skills, or meet personal and financial needs (Shishko & Rostker, 1976; Armstrong, 2020). According to Banerjee (2012), "Moonlighting refers to the practice of holding a second job in addition to a primary full-time job to supplement income or satisfy personal needs."

In the recent past, the topic of moonlighting has been the subject of heated discussion. Wipro made history by firing over 300 employees for "moonlighting" and for taking a second job outside of regular business hours. Wipro was the first big IT Company to do so. However, several IT businesses and corporations have adopted a more compassionate stance. The consensus is mixed; some businesses view it as unethical, while others see it as a necessity.

2. TYPES OF MOONLIGHTING

Blue Moonlighting: It is common for management to give in to requests from workers during performance reviews and increase compensation and benefits. However, some employees are not happy with these benefits and want to work part-time to earn extra money. But as they lack the necessary skills, their efforts may not be successful. This kind of let-down is referred to as "blue moonlighting."

Quarter moonlighting: When a worker looks for a part-time job after his main job because he is dissatisfied with his pay, it is known as quarter moonlighting. Working a quarter-time job might only be helpful for covering expenses or daily needs.

Half Moonlighting: Most workers spend more money than they make. Both luxury and putting money aside for the future are significant to them. People must work for an additional 50% of their available time to earn a sufficiently large additional amount.

Full Moonlighting: A situation in which employees in certain professions have extra time, or when they believe, their income does not compare to their expectations or when buddies with lesser qualifications enjoy a higher status than them. Due to difficult circumstances, these workers frequently establish their own company or factory while keeping their day jobs. However, the second occupation determines their social and economic standing. Full-time employment while moonlighting to this instance.

3. CONDITIONS FOR MOONLIGHTING TO TAKE PLACE

In the midst of the COVID-19 epidemic, the work from home (WFH) strategy was implemented. Following the pandemic, the strategy has persisted, with many businesses providing their staff with flexible work schedules. Many employees now have the option to work in other fields because they are no longer restricted by the need to be physically present in offices. Technology, like online video conferencing, cloud storage, and online workspaces, which permit the exchange of information/documents, have made remote working possible. Because they don't have to go physically on their jobs, this makes moonlighting easier.

In the gig economy, workers are hired on a part-time basis. Due to their part-time jobs, gig workers' employment conditions are substantially more flexible. Therefore, gig workers can have various positions.

Digital Economy: A wide range of fresh opportunities have emerged as a result of the digital economy. After hours, many people work part-time as social media influencers or start exploring more outside the corporate world.

4. ADVANTAGES OF MOONLIGHTING

Financial advantages: Working a second job enables individuals to supplement their income. This makes it easier for them to pay their debts and raises their level of living.

Up-skilling: Working a second job might open up prospects for additional education and training. Upskilling can increase job security because highly qualified people are frequently the last to be laid off during economic downturns.

Expanding Possibilities: The opportunities for workers can increase by taking on a second job. Many individuals who have been employed by the same company for a long time may experience tunnel vision, or the inability to look beyond their own field and their own position in the organization. Learning about your core field can give you a great level of exposure and knowledge and it can also provide a better future in the field.

Increasing Your Network: Taking on a second job gives you the chance to increase your network of coworkers and business contacts. A strong network is beneficial for future employment prospects.

Longer Retention: According to some experts, moonlighting can encourage workers to remain in their positions longer because it relieves them of the temptation to hunt for additional sources of income.

Social Life: Office co-workers' and other employees make up a sizable portion of one's social life. Additionally, having multiple employment can increase them to get better opportunities in the current competent market.

5. GENERAL WELL BEING

Well-being is a multifaceted construct and while there is no consensus on a single definition, the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) describes well-being as “the presence of positive emotions and moods, the absence of negative emotions, satisfaction with life, fulfillment, and positive functioning .”Siwach (2000) defines it as the "harmonious functioning of the physical as well as psychological aspects of the personality, giving satisfaction to the self and benefit to the society.”

6. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Koomson, I., Ball, L., & Kirkegaard, A. (2026) investigate the link between moonlighting and subjective wellbeing among Australians. Found that moonlighting is associated with a decrease in subjective wellbeing by 2.431 (relative to an average wellbeing score of 7.92 out of 10). The negative association between moonlighting and subjective wellbeing was more pronounced among males, urban residents, high-income earners, and those living in high socioeconomic areas.

Kendla & Deeksha (2025) analyses the different ways in which moonlighting affects the health and well-being of rural women, both positively and negatively. A mixed methods approach was used for the research. It was found that although rural women benefit economically from moonlighting and are financially empowered, it has a significant impact on their physical and mental health. Thousands of working women engage in overtime work because of the dire economic and social conditions that allow for extreme poverty, sleep deprivation and chronic fatigue. While juggling multiple jobs tends to improve one's financial

situation, it also carries the risk of increased physical exhaustion, psychological stress and inadequate access to medical facilities.

Vipanchi et al (2023) analyse the determinants that influence the employees engaging in moonlighting and its possible impact on health, well-being and productivity at large. They found that most of the employees resorted to moonlighting not only to meet their financial needs but also to satisfy their hedonic needs as it was found that the employees skills, immensely improved because of moonlighting and also it has helped them to keep themselves abreast of the latest technology, policies and strengthened their network. However it was also found that the employees were subject to prolonged stress which impacted their overall health and wellbeing.

Research Methodology

Research design

The Quantitative Cross sectional research design will be used. Difference between moonlighting and non-moonlighting adults' general wellbeing will be studied.

Variables

- Independent variable: Moonlighting
- Dependent variable: General well being

Operational Definitions of Variables

1. Moonlighting

Moonlighting is operationally defined as engagement in any paid employment or income-generating activity in addition to one's primary full-time job. In the present study, moonlighting was measured using a self-report question where participants indicated whether they engaged in additional paid work. Participants who reported involvement in secondary employment were categorized as moonlighters.

2. General Well-Being

General well-being is operationally defined as the level of positive mental health experienced by an individual during the past two weeks.

In this study, it was measured using the WHO-5 Well-Being Index, consisting of five positively worded items rated on a six-point Likert scale ranging from 0 (At no time) to 5 (All of the time). The raw total score (0–25) was multiplied by four to obtain a final score ranging from 0 to 100, with higher scores indicating greater well-being.

7 .OBJECTIVE

To measure the difference in general well-being among moonlighting and non-moonlighting employees.

HYPOTHESIS

H0: There will be no significant difference in general well-being between moonlighting and non-moonlighting employees.

Sample

The sample consists of 30 adult Indian employees with and without moonlighting experience. The purposive sampling has been done to ensure moonlighters are involved.

Inclusion Criteria

Participants were included in the study if they met the following criteria:

- Individuals currently engaged in full-time employment.
- Adults aged between 25 to 35 years of age.
- Individuals who were able to read and understand the questionnaire language.
- Participants who voluntarily consented to participate in the study. For the moonlighting group, individuals engaged in at least one additional paid job apart from their primary employment.
- For the non-moonlighting group, individuals engaged exclusively in a single primary job without any secondary paid employment.

Exclusion Criteria

Participants were excluded from the study if they met any of the following conditions:

- Individuals who were unemployed, retired, or students without full-time employment.
- Individuals engaged only in unpaid voluntary work as secondary activity.
- Participants who provided incomplete or inconsistent responses in the questionnaire.
- Individuals below 25 and above 35 years of age.
- Participants who did not provide informed consent.

Measurement Tools

The details of the scales that have been used in the study are as follows:-

General Moonlighting Questionnaire: This is a general scale consisting of questions related to moonlighting, like moonlighting job, reason for moonlighting, hours spent in moonlighting, whether it hinders their work-life balance, etc.

The World Health Organization-Five Well-Being Index (WHO-5): The WHO-5 was developed during the 1990s by the late Per Beech of the Psychiatric Centre North Zealand (Copenhagen, Denmark). The WHO-5 is a self-report instrument measuring mental well-being. It consists of five statements relating to the past two weeks. Each statement is rated on a 6-point scale, with higher scores indicating better mental well-being.

General Information Questionnaire: - It is a basic questionnaire which gives insight to an individual 'consent and demographic details.

Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was conducted using descriptive statistics and an independent samples t-test to examine the difference between moonlighters and non-moonlighters on general wellbeing.

8. RESULT

In the following chapter, statistical analysis and findings of the study conducted to examine the difference in general well-being between moonlighters and non-moonlighters are presented. The results are presented in the following table-

Group	N	Mean	SD	t	p
Moonlighters	15	47.20	23.28	-2.61	.015
Non-moonlighters	15	67.93	17.85		

Table 1: Comparison of Well-Being Scores Between Moonlighters and Non-Moonlighters (N = 30)
Source: Author Compiled

An independent sample t-test was conducted to compare well-being scores between moonlighters and non-moonlighters. There was a significant difference in scores for moonlighters ($M = 47.20$, $SD = 23.28$) and non-moonlighters ($M = 66.93$, $SD = 17.85$); the value of $t(28)$ is -2.61 , $p = .015$. There is a significant difference of general wellbeing between moon lighting and non-moonlighting employees. Thus the Hypothesis, There is no significant difference in general well-being between moonlighting and non-moonlighting employees, is not accepted. The results indicate that individuals engaged in moonlighting reported significantly lower levels of well-being compared to non-moonlighters.

Interpretation

The present study aimed to examine differences in general well-being between moonlighters and non-moonlighters. The results revealed a statistically significant difference between the two groups. Non-moonlighters reported significantly higher well-being scores compared to individuals engaged in moonlighting. The obtained t-value, $t(28) = -2.61$, with $p = .015$, indicates that the difference between groups is unlikely to have occurred by chance.

The mean well-being score of moonlighters ($M = 47.20$) was considerably lower than that of non-moonlighters ($M = 66.93$).

The findings may be interpreted through the lens of role strain theory, which posits that individuals occupying multiple demanding roles may experience stress due to limited personal resources such as time, energy, and emotional capacity. Moonlighting may increase workload, reduce recovery time, and disrupt work-life balance. The cumulative burden of managing dual employment responsibilities may lead to fatigue, emotional exhaustion, and decreased vitality, all of which are components of general well-being measured by the WHO-5.

Another possible explanation is related to the concept of resource depletion. Engaging in secondary employment may limit opportunities for rest, leisure activities, and social interaction. Over time, this imbalance may negatively affect mood, motivation, and overall life satisfaction.

However, it is important to interpret the findings cautiously. Moonlighting may be motivated by financial necessity, career advancement, or personal growth. In some contexts, secondary employment may enhance self-efficacy and skill development which can be explained through theory of role expansion. Therefore, the relationship between moonlighting and well-being may depend on moderating variables such as financial stress, voluntary choice, job satisfaction, and hours spent in additional work.

9. LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The present study has certain limitations-

- The sample size was small ($N = 30$), limiting generalizability.
- The study used a cross-sectional design, preventing causal conclusions.
- Data were collected through self-report measures, which may be influenced by response bias.
- The study did not examine moderating variables such as financial stress, job satisfaction, or voluntary versus compulsory moonlighting.

10. CONCLUSION

The present study examined the difference in general well-being between moonlighters and non-moonlighters. The findings revealed a statistically significant difference between the two groups, with non-moonlighters reporting higher levels of well-being than moonlighters.

The results suggest that engaging in additional paid employment alongside a primary job may be associated with reduced general well-being. While moonlighting may provide financial or professional benefits, it may also increase workload, role strain, and fatigue, thereby negatively influencing mental health.

Overall, the study highlights the psychological implications of dual employment and contributes to understanding how contemporary work patterns affect well-being.

11. SUGGESTIONS FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

- Future studies should use larger and more diverse samples.
- Longitudinal designs can help determine causal relationships.
- Moderation analysis may be conducted using variables such as gender, age, financial stress, or work-life balance.
- Qualitative research may explore personal experiences of moonlighters.
- Future studies can examine whether voluntary moonlighting differs psychologically from financially compelled moonlighting.

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